

Behaviour and design resistance of long bolts in shear

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ABSTRACT

The European standard EN 1993-1-8 lacks specific design provisions for bolted connections incorporating long bolts, despite their increasing use in innovative joint configurations. Long bolts are defined as structural bolts that are manufactured from circular steel, fully or partially, threaded rods instead of a steel coil and are not subjected to heat treatment. In contrast to standard structural bolts, they do not present a bolt head. They are assembled with standard washers and nuts at both ends and feature an extended length compared to standard bolts, offering unique advantages in addressing challenges that conventional bolts cannot resolve. Within the framework of the RFCS CONNECT4C project, which focuses on promoting circular economy principles in steel construction, adaptable and reusable steel joints are being developed, with long bolts playing a key structural role. As part of this initiative, the present study explores the mechanical performance of long bolts subject to shear through an extensive experimental campaign involving 60 tests. The aim is to characterise their behaviour and assess the applicability of the existing EN 1993-1-8 formulations for shear resistance and stiffness to this specific bolt type. Finally, a reliability assessment is conducted to establish a suitable partial factor (γ_{M2}) for connections utilising long bolts, confirming that the values for standard bolts are appropriate for long bolts in shear. The outcomes provide direct guidance for incorporating long bolts into future CEN product standards and extend the current design provisions of EN 1993-1-8 to long bolts.

Symbols and acronyms

Acronyms

B Black surface of the long bolt
CoV Coefficient of variation
G Galvanised surface of the long bolt
GL Grip length
LC Load cell
LVDT Linear velocity displacement transducer
PC Property class

Latin letters

A Gross cross-section area
 A_s Tensile area of a bolt
 $A_{s,meas}$ Measured tensile area of a bolt
 $A_{s,nom}$ Nominal tensile area of a bolt

a Plate thickness
 b Plate width, Correction factor
 d External diameter of a fully threaded bolt
 d_{M16} External diameter of the M16 bolt
 E Young's modulus of bolt material
 F Force
 F_m Maximum force
 F_u Ultimate force
 $F_{v,Rd}$ Design shear resistance of bolt
 $F_{v,Rk}$ Characteristic shear resistance of bolt
 $F_{0,0048d}$ Force at the beginning of bolt yielding
 f_{ub} Bolt tensile strength
 $f_{ub,meas}$ Measured bolt tensile strength
 $f_{ub,nom}$ Nominal bolt tensile strength
 H_r LVDT measuring relative horizontal displacement
 h Horizontal measurement of the long bolt hole
 K_v Initial stiffness of a bolt
 $K_{v,EN}$ Initial stiffness of a bolt according to EN 1993-1-8

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$K_{v,exp}$	Experimental initial stiffness of a bolt
$K_{v,prop.}$	Proposed formula for initial stiffness of a long bolt
k_r	Reduction factor to account for the length of a bolted lap connection
k_{rd}	Reduction factor to account for the reduced ductility of grade 10.9 bolts
k_v	Stiffness coefficient for bolts in shear according to EN 1993-1-8
L	Total bolt length
L_g	Grip length
L_m	Distance between LVDT_11 and LVDT_13
n_n	Number of shear planes with threads intercepting the shear plane
n_x	Number of shear planes without threads intercepting the shear plane
OV	Holes ovalisation
R	Circular radius of bolt curvature
u	Shear deformation of bolts
$u_{i,exp}$	Isolated displacement component in the bolt middle
u_0	Correction of the initial slip
Δu_i	Relative displacement between plates for load application
$\Delta u_{i,c}$	Corrected value of the relative displacement between plates for load application
V_a	LVDT measuring absolute vertical displacement
V_r	LVDT measuring relative vertical displacement
V_δ	Estimator for the coefficient of variation
v	Vertical measurement of the long bolt holes

Greek letters

α_v	Shear coefficient
β	Reliability index
γ_{M2}	Partial factor
Δ_{el}	Elastic deformation
θ	Angle of bolt rotation
ϕ	Resistance factor, Capacity factor

1. Introduction

Bolted connections are a fundamental component in steel structures, valued for their simplicity, ease of assembly, and potential for disassembly and reuse. Design standards such as the European standard EN 1993-1-8 [1] provide detailed guidance for the design of these connections, assembled with preloaded (EN 14399) [2] or non-preloaded (EN 15048) [3] bolts. However, recent trends in structural engineering, driven by sustainability and modular construction, are encouraging the development and use of non-standard connection solutions. Among these innovations, long bolts are gaining increased attention.

Long bolts, also known as bi-directional [4] or stud bolts [3], characterised by their extended grip lengths, offer distinct advantages over conventional bolts in specific structural applications. They are particularly useful in connections involving thick intermediate plates, multiple joint components, or wider spacing between connected elements. They are also used in joints with concrete-filled tubes [5]–[6], as foundation anchors and for self-centring solutions aiming to improve the seismic response of the structure, as reported in [7–8]. Their ability to bridge larger gaps and facilitate adaptable joint configurations makes them especially suitable for reusable systems. Nevertheless, their mechanical behaviour remains insufficiently explored in existing design standards and available literature. The current provisions of EN 1993-1-8 were developed for conventional bolts with relatively short lengths. These formulas may not be directly applicable to long bolts, as their manufacturing processes and the increased length can lead to different failure modes, load distribution, and stiffness characteristics.

The present research is conducted within the framework of the RFCS CONNECT4C project [9], which focuses on developing adaptable and

Fig. 1. - Geometry of a structural long bolt (adapted from [10]).

reusable steel joints to support the circular economy in structural engineering. Long bolts are a critical component of these new joints, and their proper characterisation is critical for ensuring safe and efficient design. To address this need, the present study investigates the mechanical performance of long bolts under shear loading, complementing a previously published paper [10] that addressed long bolts in tension. A total of 60 experimental tests were conducted to evaluate their shear resistance and stiffness. The results are analysed and compared against the corresponding design provisions for standard bolts in shear as outlined in EN 1993-1-8. Special emphasis is placed on assessing the validity of the shear coefficient (α_v) for long bolts. Finally, a reliability assessment is performed to validate the applicability of the partial factor (γ_{M2}) for connections incorporating long bolts in shear.

2. Background review

2.1. Geometry of the long bolts

The manufacturing process of long bolts differs significantly from that of standard bolts. Unlike standard bolts, which are typically made of steel coil and undergo heat treatment during production, long bolts are fabricated from steel rods without any subsequent heat treatment. A detailed description of their manufacturing process is provided in reference [10]. These bolts are usually available in lengths up to 1000 mm, though they can be cut to shorter sizes based on client specifications.

In this study, fully threaded long bolts were used. Unlike conventional bolts, they do not feature a forged head. Instead, they are equipped with nuts and washers (HV in the present study) at both ends to create the necessary clamping force.

The dimensions of a long bolt are illustrated in Fig. 1. The total length of the bolt is denoted as L , L_g is the grip length, and d is the external diameter of the bolt. The calculation of the tensile stress area A_s , referenced throughout this text, follows the provisions specified in ISO 898-1 [11].

2.2. Behaviour of structural bolts in shear

2.2.1. Standard structural bolts

Many studies have investigated the shear strength and behaviour of high-strength bolts under various load scenarios, including tension, shear and their combination, through experimental and numerical studies.

Stranghöner et al. [12] conducted a comprehensive literature review on high-strength bolts, compiling relevant findings from previous experimental studies on their behaviour in tension, shear, and the interaction of both, and reviewed design expressions for the resistance of carbon steel bolts as specified in EN 1993-1-8 [1], AISC 360-22 [13], and AS 4100 [14]. In addition to reviewing existing research, Stranghöner et al. [12] carried out their own experimental investigations and performed statistical validation through a reliability analysis following EN 1990 Annex D [15]. Their study highlighted the significance of the shear coefficient α_v in the shear resistance formula prescribed by EN 1993-1-8 [1], proposing a value of 0.65 for bolt classes 8.8 and 10.9, applicable to both threaded and unthreaded sections in the shear plane. Furthermore, they established a correlation between bolt tensile strength and shear coefficient, demonstrating an inverse

relationship whereby an increase in tensile strength corresponds to a decrease in the shear coefficient. In Stranghöner and Abraham [16], a similar approach was used for austenitic and duplex stainless-steel bolts. They evaluated the shear coefficients α_v for these bolts, which are higher than the ones defined in EN 1993-1-4 [17].

Wallaert and Fisher [18] identified two methods for testing the shear strength of bolts: using plates in tension or compression. Their findings indicate that, because of lap plate prying action, bolts tested under tension exhibit shear strengths 6–13 % lower than those tested under compression and with lower scatter, which makes the test in tension the preferred testing layout. Additionally, Kulak et al. [19] reported that the shear strength to tensile strength ratio is independent of bolt class and is approximately 62 %. Li et al. [20] highlighted the influence of the shear plane position on the shear strength for 10.9-class bolts. Their study demonstrated that when the shear plane passes through the unthreaded shank, the shear capacity reaches approximately 80 % of the bolt's tensile strength. However, when the shear plane passes through the threaded section, the shear capacity decreases to around 60 % of the bolt's tensile strength. Considering that the gross area to tensile area ratio of the bolts in the study was approximately 1.28, the results are in good agreement with those by Stranghöner et al. [12].

Xin et al. [21] conducted a numerical study on the behaviour of bolts under combined loading, incorporating the precise geometry of bolt threads in their models to enhance accuracy. Their study assessed the reliability of existing design standards by comparing the simulated shear resistance with the predictions provided by various codes. The results indicated that the simulated shear strength exceeded the values calculated using the EN 1993-1-8 expressions by 6 % for partially threaded bolts and by 22 % for fully threaded bolts. Authors [21] further concluded that the American AISC-360 [13], Chinese GB-50017 [22], and Australian AS 4100 [14] standards provide reliable estimates for the shear resistance of partially threaded bolts but tend to overestimate the resistance of fully threaded bolts.

Numerous studies have been conducted to assess the behaviour of lap joint configurations, whereby the bolts work in shear, and it is required to establish appropriate geometrical criteria to prevent either the shear failure of the bolt or the splitting failure/shear failure of the connecting plates. In this context, significant research efforts have been dedicated to studying the bearing resistance of bolt holes. Može and Beg [23–25]

improved and extended the applicability of the bearing resistance equations to high-strength steel plates. As a result, Može and Piculin [26] developed an analytical formula to predict the full range force-deformation behaviour of steel plates at bolt holes. This formulation was included in the revised version of EN 1993-1-8 [27]. In particular, an alternative initial stiffness expression is provided for the load-deformation behaviour of bolt embedment due to bearing action that gives a high level of accuracy.

In contrast, studies focusing on the full range shear behaviour of bolts in shear, where the failure mode is the shear resistance of the bolt instead of plate bearing, are scarcer. Karmalin and Pavlov [28] carried out tests on bolts in shear with very high-strength steel plates (tensile strength $f_{ub} \geq 2000$ MPa) to prevent bearing deformations. Based on this study, Jaspert [29] proposed Eq. (1) for the initial stiffness of one bolt in single shear, K_v (kN/mm):

$$K_v = 0.93A_s f_{ub}, \tag{1}$$

where the constant 0.93 has units of millimetres (mm), A_s is the tensile stress area of the bolt in mm^2 , and f_{ub} is the nominal tensile strength of the bolt in kN/mm^2 .

Eq. (1) was adjusted in EN 1993-1-8 [1] to avoid dependence on units, as follows:

$$K_v = k_v E = \frac{8d^2}{d_{M16}} f_{ub}, \tag{2}$$

where k_v is the bolt shear stiffness normalised by Young's modulus E , d is the nominal bolt diameter, and d_{M16} is the nominal diameter of an M16 bolt. Eq. (2) correlates well with Eq. (1), giving results approximately 13.5 % lower to match the 95th percentile of the results of the Karmalin and Pavlov tests.

Ahmed and Teh [30] assessed the influence of shear on the threaded part of a bolt, showing a reduction of approximately 56 % of the initial stiffness compared to shear in the shank due to the threads cutting into the plates. However, in their tests, "the connection displacements were almost entirely due to the bolt hole deformation". Lange [31] tested standard M20 bolts of grades 8.8 and 10.9 in single and double shear. His results confirm that there is a reduction in the initial stiffness of bolts with a shear plane on the threaded part when compared to the shear

Table 1
Design specifications for bolts in shear in EN 1993-1-8 [27], AISC 360–22 [13] and AS 4100 [14].

Shear resistance		
EN 1993-1-8 [27] Shear plane in the threaded part	$F_{v,Rd} = \frac{\alpha_v f_{ub} A_s}{\gamma_{M2}}$	$\alpha_v = \begin{cases} 0.6 & \text{for PC 4.6, 5.6, 8.8} \\ 0.5 & \text{for PC 4.8, 5.8, 6.8, 10.9} \end{cases}$
Shear plane in the unthreaded part	$F_{v,Rd} = \frac{\alpha_v f_{ub} A}{\gamma_{M2}}$	$\alpha_v = 0.6$ for all PC
AISC 360–22 [13] Shear plane in the threaded part	$F_{v,Rd,AISC} = \phi 0.45 f_{ub} A$	
Shear plane in the unthreaded part	$F_{v,Rd,AISC} = \phi 0.563 f_{ub} A$	
AS 4100 [14] Shear plane in the threaded part	$F_{v,Rd,AS} = \phi 0.62 f_{ub} k_{rd} k_r n_x A_s$	$k_{rd} = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{for PC 4.6, 8.8} \\ 0.83 & \text{for PC 10.9} \end{cases}$
Shear plane in the unthreaded part	$F_{v,Rd,AS} = \phi 0.62 f_{ub} k_{rd} k_r n_x A$	$k_{rd} = 1.0$ for all PC
Initial stiffness (for one bolt-row, with two bolts per bolt-row, normalised to the Young Modulus E)		
EN 1993-1-8 [27] Non-preloaded bolts (bearing type connection)	$k_v = \frac{16d^2 f_{ub}}{E d_{M16}}$	
Preloaded bolts (slip-resistant connection)	$k_v = \infty$	

α_v : shear coefficient | f_{ub} : nominal tensile strength of the bolt | A_s : tensile stress area of the bolt | A : gross cross-section area of the bolt | γ_{M2} : partial factor ($\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$) | d : nominal diameter of the bolt | ϕ : resistance factor according to AISC 360–22 ($\phi = 0.75$ (LRFD)), and capacity factor according to AS 4100 ($\phi = 0.80$ for bolts in shear) | k_{rd} : reduction factor to account for the reduced ductility of grade 10.9 bolts | k_r : reduction factor to account for the length of a bolted lap connection ($k_r = 1.0$ for other connections) | n_x : number of shear planes with threads intersecting the shear plane | n_x : number of shear planes without threads intersecting the shear plane | E : Young's modulus of steel | d_{M16} : nominal diameter of an M16 bolt | PC: bolt's property class.

Fig. 2. Studied grip lengths.

Table 2
Summary of the performed tests.

Bolt size	Class	Surface finish	Grip length L_g (mm)	Plate thickness a (mm)	No. of tests (-)
M20	8.8 and 10.9	B and G	60, 220, 380 and 540	10	24
M24	8.8 and 10.9	B and G	60, 220, 380 and 540	10	20
M27	10.9	B and G	60, 220, 380 and 540	15	8
M30	10.9	B and G	60, 220, 380 and 540	15	8
				Total	Σ 60

plane on the shank.

Henriques et al. [32] proposed a trilinear full-range law for the bolt in shear, establishing their strain hardening stiffness, ultimate resistance, and ultimate deformation, based on the Karmalin and Pavlov tests. The model incorporates parameters expressed as functions of the initial stiffness and nominal resistance.

In summary, the reviewed literature on standard bolts does not provide much information that can be used to identify specific aspects that may be critical for long bolts. However, the reviewed papers allow for establishing reference results and procedures for the assessment of the shear resistance and initial stiffness of bolts in shear. Additionally, they also provide guidance on the testing methods for bolts in shear and how to minimise bearing deformations in the testing process.

2.2.2. Long bolts

Long bolts have received limited attention in existing literature and design standards. Janković et al. [10] conducted a literature review on the behaviour of long threaded rods under tensile loading, highlighting the need for further research in this area. Consequently, the present study focuses on the behaviour of long bolts subjected to shear forces, addressing a gap in the current understanding of their structural performance.

The majority of the studies have investigated the behaviour of long bolts in end-plate beam-to-column joints with concrete-filled tubular steel columns [4]–[6]. The primary objective of using long bolts in such configurations is to solve the problem of having no access to the inside of the tubes, enhancing joint rigidity and resistance while minimising the number of additional components required for assembly, such as U-channels, blind bolts [5], fin plates, angle, or tee cleats. Experimental testing on long bolts passing through concrete-filled tubular columns has demonstrated that bolt bending has no significant influence on joint performance. Based on these findings, Van-Long et al. [5] recommended the application of the shear resistance formula from EN 1993-1-8, originally developed for standard bolts, to long bolts as well.

Fransplass et al. [33] investigated the behaviour of long bolts manufactured from threaded rods under tensile loading and combined tension and shear, considering both low and elevated strain rates. The experiments were conducted using a custom-designed fixture, allowing for the examination of different grip lengths ranging from 0.41 mm to

9.8 mm. Their findings revealed that the ultimate load in shear tests increases with the loading rate, indicating a strain rate sensitivity in the material response. Additionally, fracture surface analysis showed a smooth appearance with a slight inclination following the thread pitch, suggesting a failure mode influenced by the bolt's threading geometry. However, since they tested small grip lengths and small diameter rods in mild steel, M5 class 4.6, the validity of their conclusions for the present study may be limited.

2.3. Design resistance and initial stiffness of bolts under shear loading

Design standards differentiate the shear resistance depending on whether the shear plane passes through the unthreaded or threaded portion of the bolt. Table 1 summarises the expressions for shear resistance and initial stiffness of a bolt in shear according to the revised version of EN 1993-1-8 [27], AISC 360-22 [13] and AS 4100 [14].

The formula for initial stiffness defined in EN 1993-1-8 considers two bolts per bolt row and a single shear plane. Hence, for a single bolt and a single shear plane, Eq. (6a) must be divided by 2, effectively coinciding with Eq. (2). Furthermore, it is noted that EN 1993-1-8 [27] explicitly separates the initial stiffness of the bolt in shear (addressed in this paper) that only covers the deformability of the bolt (not the connecting plates) from the initial stiffness of the bolt in bearing (that only covers the deformability of the connecting plates). The total initial stiffness of the bolt-plate assembly consists of the addition of both initial stiffnesses.

3. Experimental programme

3.1. Programme definition

The experimental campaign aims to characterise the behaviour of long bolts in shear. To achieve this objective, F - u curves for the long bolts are extracted, where F represents the total applied shear force (including the two shear planes, see Fig. 4) and u denotes the relative displacement of the shearing plates due to the deformability of the bolt.

A total of 60 tensile tests were performed, covering the following parameters:

- Bolt diameter (M20, M24, M27 and M30),

Table 3
Nominal geometry and resistance of the bolts.

Bolt notation			M20	M24	M27	M30
Bolt diameter	<i>d</i>	mm	20	24	27	30
Thread pitch	<i>P</i>	mm	2.5	3.0	3.0	3.5
Tensile area	<i>A_s</i>	mm ²	245	353	459	561
Nut thickness (nominal)	<i>t_n</i>	mm	16	20	22	24
Washer thickness (nominal)	<i>t_w</i>	mm	4	4	5	5
Class 8.8: Characteristic shear resistance, Eq. (3a) with $\gamma_{M2} = 1.0$ and $\alpha_v = 0.60$	<i>F_{v,Rk}</i>	kN	235.2	338.9	440.6	538.6
Class 10.9: Characteristic shear resistance, Eq. (3a) with $\gamma_{M2} = 1.0$ and $\alpha_v = 0.50$	<i>F_{v,Rk}</i>	kN	245.0	353.0	459.0	561.0
Class 8.8: Characteristic shear resistance, Eq. (4a) with $\phi = 1.0$	<i>F_{v,Rk,AISC}</i>	kN	226.2	325.7	412.2	508.9
Class 10.9: Characteristic shear resistance, Eq. (4a) with $\phi = 1.0$	<i>F_{v,Rk,AISC}</i>	kN	282.7	407.2	515.3	636.2
Class 8.8: Characteristic shear resistance, Eq. (5a) with $\phi = 1.0$ and $k_{rd} = 1.0$	<i>F_{v,Rk,AS}</i>	kN	243.0	350.2	455.3	556.5
Class 10.9: Characteristic shear resistance, Eq. (5a) with $\phi = 1.0$ and $k_{rd} = 0.83$	<i>F_{v,Rk,AS}</i>	kN	252.2	363.3	472.4	577.4

- Bolt property class (8.8 and 10.9),
- Surface finish (B – black, uncoated and G – galvanised, zinc-coated),
- Grip lengths excluding washers (60, 220, 380 and 540 mm), see Fig. 2.

All tests were performed with one washer and nut per bolt side. Each test was labelled by combining the letter “S” (representing shear) with the specifications of its defining parameters. For example, “S31-M24–10.9-B-380-P10” corresponds to the shear test (S), number of the test (31st), long bolt M24 in steel property class 10.9, with a black (B) surface finish, with a grip length of 380 mm and plate thickness of 10 mm (P10). A summary of all performed tests, with varying parameters, is given in Table 2.

Two tests (S31-M24–10.9-B-380-P10 and S48-M30–10.9-G-540-P15) were excluded from the analysis due to instrumentation malfunctions, leaving, in total, 58 valid tests for post-processing.

The thickness of the plates for load application is 10 mm for smaller bolt diameters (M20 and M24) and 15 mm for larger bolt diameters (M27 and M30). All tests with longer grip lengths (GL220, GL380, and GL540) involved two plates at each bolt ending. For the shortest grip length (GL60), the number of plates used was six (for M20 and M24 bolts) or four (for M27 and M30 bolts). The nominal hole diameters are in accordance with EN 1090–2 [34]: 22 mm, 26 mm, 30 mm, and 33 mm for M20, M24, M27, and M30 bolts, respectively.

Table 3 contains the geometry of the bolts with corresponding nuts and washers’ thicknesses, and the unfactored shear resistance according to EN 1993-1-8 [27], AISC 360–22 [13] and AS 4100 [14].

Comparing AISC 360–22 and AS 4100 with EN 1993-1-8, the following differences are noted: the unfactored shear resistance values for 8.8 and 10.9 bolt classes, respectively, are 3.8 % lower and 15.4 % higher for AISC 360–22 and 3.3 % and 2.9 % higher for AS 4100. Comparing the factored results, the corresponding results are 9.9 % lower and 8.2 % higher for AISC 360–22 and 3.3 % and 2.9 % higher for AS 4100.

3.2. Experimental layout

The experimental layout is presented in Fig. 3. It consists of permanent parts (labels 1–4 and 6–10) and replaceable parts (specimens and parts with labels 5, 11, and 12), presented in Fig. 3(a). The reaction frame (6) consists of two vertical columns and a strong beam that works as a support for the 6 MN hydraulic jack (10). With the hinge (9), the jack fixes the upper retaining beam (2) and pulls it up during the load application phase. The bottom retaining beam (1) is positioned in the lower part of the layout. Its movement is restricted by the supporting

brackets (7) and two load cells (8) that measure the vertical reactions.

Both upper and bottom retaining beams have a guiding system (4) that ensures they slide easily on the reaction frame columns. Plates for load application (5), which are fixed between angular plates (3) and spacers (11,12), have holes for positioning the specimens. When the load

Fig. 3. Test layout: (a) 2D view with marked parts; (b) 3D view; (c) Photo from the test.

Fig. 4. Instrumentation (all dimensions in millimetres).

is applied with the hydraulic jack, the upper retaining beam (2) is pulled up together with the load application plates (5) connected to it. The load application plates (5) connected to the bottom retaining beam (1) are fixed, and hence, the specimen is subjected to shear forces. To accurately assess the shear capacity of long bolts, it is essential to minimise friction between the plates. This was achieved by applying lubricant to the contact surfaces of both the internal and external plates. Strong bars (13) are utilised to prevent the opening of load application plates (5) and to fix the constant grip length during the test performance. Since the primary objective of the experimental campaign is to evaluate the shear resistance of the bolts, the bearing deformation of the plates needs to be minimised. This is achieved by using thick plates made of high-strength steel S690. Ideally, the plates remain undamaged while the long bolts undergo shear deformation and subsequent failure.

3.3. Test procedure and instrumentation

The test was performed by applying a displacement to the upper retaining beam, using a 6 MN hydraulic jack attached to the beam with a

pin connection. The test speed was 0.025 mm/s. During the tests, the following data were acquired (see Fig. 4):

- Applied force and reactions, using load cells (LCs);
- Displacements, using LVDTs (Linear Velocity Displacement Transducers).

Two 2 MN-capacity load cells, labelled LC-1 and LC-2, were used for load measurements. They were positioned between the lower retaining beams and the supporting brackets.

In total, 13 LVDTs were used to measure vertical absolute (label V_a), vertical relative (label V_r), and horizontal relative (label H_r) displacements of parts of the test. LVDTs $V_r - 7$ and 8 measured the relative vertical displacement between the external and internal plates for load and were positioned symmetrically on both sides of the layout. Four LVDTs ($V_a - 1, 2, 3,$ and 4) were positioned on the upper retaining beam to assess potential beam rotation during test execution. LVDTs $V_a - 5$ and 6 , positioned on the top flange along the axis of the bottom retaining beam, monitored the potential bending or rotation of the bottom

Table 4
Geometrical (considering only bolts with black surface) and material characterisation [10].

Bolt	Class	Tensile stress area $A_{s,meas}$		$A_{s,meas} / A_{s,nom}$		Tensile strength $f_{ub,meas}$		$f_{ub,meas} / f_{ub,nom}$	
		Mean (mm ²)	No. of meas. (-)	Mean (-)	CoV (%)	Mean (MPa)	No. of coupon tests (-)	Mean (-)	CoV (%)
M20	8.8	229.52	9	0.94	0.77	950.61	6	1.19	1.14
	10.9	240.47	9	0.98	0.28	1176.15	6	1.18	3.24
	Both	235.00	18	0.96	2.46	-	12	1.18	2.37
M24	8.8	344.84	9	0.98	0.91	995.87	6	1.24	4.30
	10.9	342.34	9	0.97	0.34	1166.58	6	1.17	0.93
	Both	343.59	18	0.97	0.76	-	12	1.21	4.56
M27	8.8	-	-	-	-	1013.73	4	1.27	0.53
	10.9	441.27	9	0.96	0.60	1183.33	6	1.18	0.47
	Both	441.27	9	0.96	0.60	-	10	1.21	3.59
M30	8.8	-	-	-	-	984.70	4	1.23	1.80
	10.9	549.82	9	0.98	0.26	1187.03	5	1.19	1.26
	Both	549.82	9	0.98	0.25	-	9	1.21	2.39
All	8.8	-	18	0.96	2.33	983.63	20	1.23	3.45
	10.9	-	36	0.97	0.98	1177.89	23	1.18	1.83
	All	-	54	0.97	1.72	-	43	1.20	3.47

Fig. 5. Force-displacement curves: (a) GL60; (b) GL220; (c) GL380; (d) GL540.

Table 5
Summary of the shear test results of the long bolts.

Bolt	Class	Grip length L_g (mm)	No. of tests (-)	Initial stiffness K_v (kN/mm)		Force at yielding point $F_{0.0048d}$ (kN)		Displ. at yielding point $u_{0.0048d}$ (mm)		Maximum force F_m (kN)		Displ. at maximum force u_m (mm)		Force at last step F_u (kN)		Displ. at last step u_u (mm)		
				Mean	CoV	Mean	CoV	Mean	CoV	Mean	CoV	Mean	CoV	Mean	CoV	Mean	CoV	
M20	8.8	60	2	174.65	5.2	199.13	0.8	1.22	3.7	272.95	1.9	2.68	3.7	243.16	5.8	3.40	0.9	
		220	6	165.72	16.4	223.24	6.6	1.48	25.7	267.77	1.7	2.50	10.7	263.74	1.0	2.69	11.0	
		380	2	156.80	1.1	225.65	1.1	1.52	3.2	283.72	0.3	3.09	4.9	281.78	0.7	3.24	1.4	
		540	2	183.08	9.6	211.64	9.8	1.25	19.7	272.10	5.2	2.42	7.5	269.20	3.8	2.56	13.4	
	All	12	168.61	12.5	217.69	7.0	1.40	21.3	272.01	3.0	2.62	11.7	264.23	5.0	2.88	14.0		
	10.9	60	2	142.68	1.2	266.09	0.2	1.95	1.2	335.85	2.0	3.19	3.7	304.99	4.1	3.69	11.2	
		220	6	163.74	9.7	308.19	3.9	1.99	9.9	345.05	2.3	3.19	10.9	343.45	2.2	3.34	12.7	
		380	2	161.00	3.3	291.89	12.7	1.90	18.8	342.98	4.4	3.08	4.4	342.73	4.3	3.11	5.6	
		540	2	164.88	5.8	282.70	5.9	1.80	5.5	347.92	4.4	3.18	14.6	346.97	4.0	3.32	15.9	
	All	12	159.97	8.7	294.21	7.5	1.94	10.5	343.65	2.8	3.17	8.9	337.51	5.2	3.36	11.8		
	M24	8.8	All	24	164.29	11.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			60	2	191.98	3.0	308.05	6.3	1.70	2.5	428.69	5.2	3.66	5.6	419.19	4.3	3.92	6.0
220			4	197.50	16.0	349.38	12.1	1.93	27.3	440.13	0.2	3.57	9.4	436.22	1.2	3.72	8.4	
380			2	172.39	4.6	342.67	3.1	2.09	7.9	435.89	1.9	3.77	6.9	435.64	1.9	3.81	7.7	
10.9		540	2	164.69	13.2	341.90	4.2	2.19	5.0	438.31	3.0	4.19	2.0	424.96	4.5	4.29	0.8	
		All	10	184.81	13.3	338.28	9.0	1.97	18.0	436.63	2.3	3.75	8.8	430.44	2.8	3.89	8.1	
		60	2	166.84	7.5	394.07	7.7	2.48	18.1	474.84	3.8	3.81	6.7	464.59	1.9	4.07	8.8	
		220	4	228.45	30.4	373.66	18.0	1.92	44.1	476.07	4.5	3.56	13.9	474.63	4.3	3.64	15.9	
		380	1	164.38	-	411.52	-	2.60	-	514.59	-	4.86	-	514.24	-	4.94	-	
		540	2	177.31	2.4	383.68	1.5	2.26	1.2	489.91	0.4	4.09	5.0	488.89	0.7	4.21	6.8	
All	9	196.28	26.9	384.63	11.6	2.19	27.3	483.15	4.1	3.87	13.9	479.97	4.2	4.01	14.5			
M27	10.9	All	19	190.24	20.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		60	2	275.02	1.4	509.69	6.3	1.97	5.0	652.35	2.1	3.64	0.3	643.82	1.0	3.80	0.0	
		220	2	245.74	30.3	554.78	6.9	2.50	45.0	630.47	1.0	3.79	17.8	626.57	1.1	3.91	18.4	
		380	2	251.97	5.4	534.86	3.8	2.24	7.1	623.70	3.1	3.85	12.6	623.03	2.9	3.88	13.2	
		540	2	237.84	1.6	548.51	4.9	2.42	4.8	630.34	3.4	3.78	1.1	629.27	3.3	3.83	1.6	
		All	8	252.64	12.8	536.96	5.5	2.28	21.0	634.21	2.7	3.77	8.6	630.67	2.2	3.85	8.8	
M30	10.9	60	2	274.89	7.9	610.22	7.1	2.35	1.6	755.66	4.1	4.04	3.8	753.92	4.2	4.15	4.8	
		220	2	202.36	33.6	716.71	-	2.99	44.5	735.70	1.8	4.11	20.4	734.15	2.1	4.16	22.1	
		380	2	284.63	0.6	540.32	2.5	2.03	2.8	722.26	5.0	3.94	11.1	717.69	4.2	4.13	17.2	
		540	1	274.04	-	629.57	-	2.42	-	751.29	-	4.18	-	743.80	-	4.37	-	
		All	7	256.83	18.5	607.89	11.3	2.36	44.4	739.79	3.4	4.05	9.9	736.48	3.3	4.18	11.7	

retaining beam. In addition, three LVDTs ($V_a - 11, 12,$ and 13) were used to capture the potential bending of the long bolts. These LVDTs were not used in the GL60 tests due to the lack of space for their installation. The opening of the external plates was tracked with two horizontal LVDTs ($H_r - 9$ and 10).

3.4. Test results

3.4.1. General

The results of the experimental campaign are presented in the following sections, showing the force-displacement curves and all relevant findings systematically. The failure modes observed during the tests are discussed, and the curvature of the bolts is analysed, including the calculation of the bending moments present in the bolts. Additionally, the influence of the bearing resistance of the load application plates on the performed tests is investigated.

3.4.2. Material and geometrical properties

The material properties of the long bolts used in this experimental campaign were determined before testing by the bolt manufacturer FATOR. The manufacturer conducted coupon tests on machined cylindrical coupons extracted from the long bolts, following clause 9.7 of ISO 898-1 [11].

The geometric properties, including external and internal diameters and thread pitch, were measured using a calliper on a sample of bolts, categorised by diameter, class, and surface finish.

The long bolts used in this study were produced concurrently with those reported in [10] as part of the same broader experimental campaign under the CONNECT4C project [9]. Both campaigns utilised bolts made from steel sourced from the same batch. For the present

Fig. 6. Points of interest on the experimental curves.

study, the bolts were only cut to specific lengths, while the material and geometric properties reported in [10] are also applicable to this study. These results are summarised in Table 4. For defining the tensile stress area ($A_{s,meas}$) of the galvanised bolts, the coating was included in the cross-sectional measurements, which may lead to unsafe estimations. Therefore, in the present study, only measurements of the black bolts are considered. For further calculations, a mean tensile stress area is adopted for each bolt diameter, treating both property classes (8.8 and 10.9)

Fig. 7. Schematic representation of the corrected displacement $\Delta u_{7,c}$.

Table 6
Average $\Delta u_{7,c}/\Delta u_{8,c}$ ratios.

Grip length l_g (mm)	Bolt				
	M20	M24	M27	M30	All
60	1.30	1.09	1.26	1.36	1.24
220	1.38	1.42	2.06	1.72	1.48
380	0.92	1.16	1.63	0.89	1.11
540	1.43	1.25	0.97	1.06	1.25
All	1.29	1.27	1.48	1.28	1.31

as a single value. The average ratio of measured to nominal tensile stress area is 0.97, with a CoV of 1.72 %.

Tensile strength values ($f_{ub,meas}$) are taken as tested in [10], obtained by combining the tensile coupon tests on the exact bolt batches used in the experimental testing with additional coupon tests from different batches from the same manufacturer (not directly used in the experimental tests) to expand the database for statistical purposes, and considered separately for each bolt diameter and property class. In total, 43 coupon tests on long bolts were considered, including the 11 tests from the experimentally tested batches and 32 additional tests from other batches. Among these, 20 tests were performed on 8.8-class bolts

(4 from the tested bolt batches and 16 from other batches) and 23 tests on 10.9-class bolts (7 from the tested bolt batches and 16 from other batches). The resulting statistical characterisation (CoV) for the tensile strength (f_{ub}) is 3.45 % for the 8.8-class bolts and 1.83 % for the 10.9-class bolts.

3.4.3. Force-displacement curves

The force-displacement ($F-u$) curves are presented in Fig. 5, categorised by the grip length. Bolt classes 8.8 and 10.9 are represented in red and blue, respectively, while full and dashed lines differentiate between black and galvanised bolt surfaces. Bolt diameters and property classes are labelled next to the corresponding curves.

The y-axis represents the total force F calculated as the sum of vertical reactions recorded by the two load cells. The x-axis displays the shear deformation of the bolts, calculated as the average of the two LVDTs ($V_r - 7$ and $V_r - 8$), subtracting the elastic deformation of the connecting plates, determined according to Eq. (7):

$$u = \frac{\Delta u_7 + \Delta u_8}{2} - \Delta_{el,e} - \Delta_{el,i} - u_0 \tag{7}$$

where Δu_7 and Δu_8 are the displacements measured by LVDTs $V_r - 7$ and $V_r - 8$, respectively, $\Delta_{el,e}$ and $\Delta_{el,i}$ are the elastic deformations of the external and internal plates, respectively, calculated adopting an effective plate width of $0.5b = 150$ mm, and u_0 is the correction of the initial slip. This correction ensures that the line defining the initial stiffness (joining two points in the curve at 30 % and 60 % of the maximum achieved force F_m , [35]) intersects the origin of coordinates. The bearing deformation of the plates is not considered in Eq. (7) because it is negligible, as shown later in Section 3.4.6. The elastic deformation component of the plates is very small, less than 5 % the shear deformability of the bolts.

Table 5 presents a summary of the shear test results obtained for the long bolts, with the relevant parameters illustrated in Fig. 6. The initial stiffness (K_v), together with three characteristic points, is identified on the $F-u$ curves. The onset of yielding, marking the end of the linear elastic region, is not distinctly visible from the curves themselves. Therefore, the method prescribed in ISO 898-1 [11] is applied, using the offset line through $u = 0.0048d$, where d is the bolt diameter. The other two characteristic points correspond to the point of maximum force (F_m) with its associated displacement (u_m), and the final point on the curve (F_u, u_u).

Fig. 8. - Failure modes: (a) LS failure – test S27; (b) RS failure – test S47; (c) BS failure – test S17.

Table 7
Summary of failure modes.

Grip length L_g (mm)	No. of tests (-)	Failure mode		
		BS	RS	LS
60	12	83.3 %	8.3 %	8.3 %
220	24	-	54.2 %	45.8 %
380	11	-	36.4 %	63.6 %
540	11	-	45.5 %	54.5 %

BS: both-sided shear failure | RS: right one-sided shear failure | LS: left one-sided shear failure.

Fig. 9. Bolt curvature.

The following observations can be drawn from Table 5 and Fig. 5:

- No notable variation in either the initial stiffness or the maximum load capacity is observed among the long bolts with different grip lengths.
- No significant difference is observed in the shear resistance of bolts with different surface finishes (black and galvanised).

The slopes of the force-displacement curves obtained for the same grip length, bolt diameter, and class, but with different surface finishes (e.g., M20 8.8-class bolt with GL380, comparing black and galvanised surfaces), generally align well.

A schematic representation of the corrected displacement $\Delta u_{7,c}$ (to account for the elastic deformation of the plates, and the initial slip) is presented in Fig. 7. The average displacement ratios on two sides of the layout, $\Delta u_{7,c} / \Delta u_{8,c}$, presented in Table 6 correspond to maximum force F_m . In an ideal testing scenario, this ratio would equal 1.0, indicating a perfectly symmetrical response with no rotational effects in the layout.

As shown in Table 6, the highest average $\Delta u_{7,c} / \Delta u_{8,c}$ ratio is 2.06, observed for M27 bolts with a 220 mm grip length. Across all tests, the overall average ratio is 1.31, compatible with minor asymmetries in the test setup. Additionally, the maximum bolt rotation angle $\theta = 1.9^\circ$ is obtained in test S20-M24-10.9-G-60-P10, while the overall average is $\theta = 0.35^\circ$.

The values of $\Delta u_{7,c}$ and $\Delta u_{8,c}$ are very small, approximately of the order of 10 % of the bolt diameter for the maximum load F_m . Despite the noticeable difference in displacement ratios and rotation angles, the variation in maximum shear load is minimal (see CoV values in column 12 of Table 5), confirming that the difference in shear displacements on the two sides had no significant effect on the ultimate shear resistance.

3.4.4. Failure modes

Two main failure modes were observed, as shown in Fig. 8: (i) one-sided shear failure, with a bolt failing either on the left (LS) (see Fig. 8(a)) or right (RS) side (see Fig. 8(b)) of the layout, and (ii) both-sided shear failure (BS) (see Fig. 8(c)), with a bolt simultaneously failing in two shear planes. The one-sided failure modes are a direct consequence of the small asymmetries reported in the previous section. It is worth noting that in the case of one-sided shear failure, the other side undergoes severe deformation, leading to thread destruction and early-stage failure initiation.

Table 8
Summary of bolt curvature parameters in long bolts.

Bolt	Class	Grip length L_g (mm)	$u_{i,exp}$	$L_m / u_{i,exp}$	R	
			Mean (mm)	Mean (-)	Mean (mm)	
M20	8.8	220	1.20	110.9	1802.5	
		380	2.56	113.6	4118.6	
		540	2.74	166.3	9354.5	
		220	1.36	97.2	1580.7	
		380	2.71	108.2	3925.4	
M24	8.8	540	3.08	147.2	8281.7	
		220	0.92	143.2	2326.9	
		380	2.46	117.9	4275.0	
		540	3.37	135.3	7611.2	
		220	0.72	201.0	3266.4	
M27	10.9	380	3.32	87.5	3171.8	
		540	3.88	116.0	6524.4	
		220	0.91	124.5	1712.9	
		380	2.55	106.2	3584.6	
		540	3.61	119.6	6427.9	
M30	10.9	220	0.76	149.0	2049.1	
		380	2.64	102.4	3457.9	
		540	3.45	124.7	6702.6	
		All	All	2.00	127.8	3858.1

Fig. 10. Hole measurement directions.

In real structural applications, such asymmetries may also occur due to construction tolerances. However, they present no real practical implications as long as the loading is equally distributed between both ends of the long bolt, as a fracture at one end will almost simultaneously occur at the other end.

Table 7 presents the percentage distribution of observed failure modes for each grip length separately. According to Table 7, most tests conducted with the shortest grip length (GL60) exhibited BS failure, whereas, conversely, bolts with longer grip lengths (GL220, GL380, and GL540) exclusively failed on one side only, without an apparent trend.

3.4.5. Bolt curvature

To assess the curvature developed in the long bolts along the unsupported length, three LVDTs ($V_a - 11, 12,$ and 13) were used between the two internal plates (see Fig. 4(b)). This measurement was not feasible for the shortest studied grip length (GL60) due to the absence of free space in the bolt length for placing LVDTs. However, measurements were successfully conducted for all longer grip lengths (GL220, GL380, and GL540). The measurements obtained are schematically illustrated in Fig. 9, where $u_{11}, u_{12},$ and u_{13} are displacements that correspond to the maximum shear load F_m and are measured in LVDTs $V_a - 11, V_a - 12,$ and $V_a - 13,$ respectively. The LVDT $V_a - 12$ is centrally positioned along a long bolt, while LVDTs $V_a - 11$ and $V_a - 13$ are located 25 mm from the internal surface of the internal load application plate (see Fig. 4(b)). Parameter $u_{i,exp}$ in Fig. 9 represents the isolated component of the middle displacement u_{12} after removing the linear contribution between u_{11} and u_{13} . It captures the deviation from a purely linear interpolation, highlighting the nonlinear deformation at the midpoint. The distance L_m between these LVDTs can be determined using the following formula:

$$L_m = L_g - 2(2a + 25\text{mm}), \tag{8}$$

Table 9
Hole ovalisation measurements.

Bolt	Statistic type	Vertical measurement before test v_0	Horizontal measurement before test h_0	Vertical measurement after test v_1	Horizontal measurement after test h_1	Ovalisation OV
M20	Mean (mm)	22.07	21.88	22.26	21.89	1.01
	CoV (%)	0.51	0.88	0.26	0.65	0.73
M24	Mean (mm)	25.89	25.85	26.20	25.90	1.01
	CoV (%)	0.55	0.53	0.68	0.28	0.64
M27	Mean (mm)	29.70	29.74	29.99	29.83	1.01
	CoV (%)	0.82	0.44	1.19	0.53	0.68
M30	Mean (mm)	32.78	32.76	32.93	32.80	1.00
	CoV (%)	0.71	0.30	0.94	0.80	0.73

Fig. 11. Example of the hole deformation from test S47: (a) External plate before testing; (b) External plate after testing.

where L_g is the grip length, and a is the thickness of the plates for load application.

The central part of the bolt (length L_m) is subjected to pure bending, and its deformation can be approximated with a circular arc of radius R and chord length L_m .

Table 8 summarises the key findings from the previously described

Table 10
Comparison of experimental and code results for shear resistance.

Bolt	Class	F_m	$\alpha_v = 0.6$ for PC 8.8, and $\alpha_v = 0.5$ for PC 10.9				$\alpha_v = 0.6$ for PC 8.8 and 10.9			$\alpha_v = 0.65$ for PC 8.8 and 10.9		
			Mean (kN)	$F_{v,Rk}$	$F_m / F_{v,Rk}$		Mean (kN)	$F_m / F_{v,Rk}$		Mean (kN)	$F_m / F_{v,Rk}$	
				Mean (kN)	Mean (-)	CoV (%)		Mean (-)	CoV (%)		Mean (-)	CoV (%)
M20	8.8	272.0	268.8	1.01	3.0	268.8	1.01	3.0	291.2	0.93	3.0	
	10.9	343.6	279.3	1.23	2.8	335.2	1.03	2.8	363.1	0.95	2.8	
M24	8.8	436.6	432.2	1.01	2.3	432.2	1.01	2.3	468.2	0.93	2.3	
	10.9	483.2	398.2	1.23	0.4	477.9	1.03	0.4	517.7	0.95	0.4	
M27	10.9	634.2	520.8	1.22	2.7	625.0	1.01	2.7	677.1	0.94	2.7	
	10.9	739.8	652.9	1.13	3.4	783.4	0.94	3.4	848.7	0.87	3.4	
All	8.8	-	-	1.01	2.6	-	1.01	2.6	-	0.93	2.6	
	10.9	-	-	1.20	4.3	-	1.00	4.3	-	0.93	4.3	
	All	-	-	1.13	9.2	-	1.01	3.7	-	0.93	3.7	

analyses. As anticipated, the radius of the bolt curvature increases with an increase in the grip length, the average bow deflection being $L_m/127.8$.

Considering that the experimental values of F_m are not dependent on the bolt length, it can be concluded that the long bolts in shear behave as bolts and not as pins.

3.4.6. Holes ovalisation

The load application plates (labelled as “5” in Fig. 3(a)) contain pre-drilled holes for positioning the test specimens. These plates are fabricated from high-strength steel S690, 10 mm and 15 mm thick for the smaller (M20 and M24) and larger (M27 and M30) bolt diameters, respectively. The design intent was to prevent bearing failure in the plates, ensuring that failure occurs by bolt shear instead. To assess the potential deformation of the bolt holes, precise measurements of their dimensions were taken before and after testing, using a calliper with a precision of 0.01 mm. These measurements were taken in four directions, as illustrated in Fig. 10: (i) V – the vertical direction, aligned with the direction of the force application, (ii) H – the horizontal direction, perpendicular to the direction of the force application, (iii) D_1 – a diagonal direction at 45° to both V and H directions, and (iv) D_2 – a second diagonal direction, perpendicular to D_1 .

The hole ovalisation (OV) is assessed as the change in the aspect ratio of the hole due to deformation, providing a normalised (non-dimensional) measure of ovalisation. It is calculated using the ratio of vertical (v) to horizontal (h) measurements, according to the following formula:

$$OV = \frac{\frac{v_1}{h_1}}{\frac{v_0}{h_0}} \tag{9}$$

where v_0 and v_1 are the measurements in the vertical (V) direction before and after testing, respectively, while h_0 and h_1 are the measurements in the horizontal direction (H) before and after testing, respectively.

The results, summarised in Table 9, include the mean and CoV values for the vertical and horizontal measurements according to the bolt diameter, as well as the ovalisation values. As observed, all OV values remain close to 1.0, indicating minimal deformation.

Fig. 12. Comparison of theoretical and experimental shear resistance for long bolts: a) PC 8.8: $\alpha_v = 0.6$, PC 10.9: $\alpha_v = 0.5$; b) PC 8.8: $\alpha_v = 0.6$, PC 10.9: $\alpha_v = 0.6$; c) PC 8.8: $\alpha_v = 0.65$, PC 10.9: $\alpha_v = 0.65$.

Table 11
Effects of varying α_v on R^2 values.

Class	$\alpha_v = 0.6$ for PC 8.8, and $\alpha_v = 0.5$ for PC 10.9	$\alpha_v = 0.6$ for PC 8.8 and 10.9	$\alpha_v = 0.65$ for PC 8.8 and 10.9
8.8	0.987	0.987	0.893
10.9	0.666	0.970	0.853
All	0.798	0.981	0.901

Fig. 11 depicts the hole in the plate from test S47-M30-10.9-G-540-P15, before and after the test performance. Only a minimal surface deformation is visible at the top of the hole, but overall, the bearing deformation is negligible and is therefore excluded from further analysis. This confirms that the test failure corresponds to shear failure of the long bolts.

4. Assessment of code prescriptions

4.1. Design resistance

Table 10 compares the experimentally determined bolt shear resistance values with the corresponding resistance values calculated according to Eq. (3a), using measured material and geometrical properties of the bolts. The results show excellent agreement for 8.8-class bolts (average $F_m / F_{v,Rk}$ equal to 1.01 for M20 and M24 bolts), while Eq. (3a) underestimates the shear resistance of 10.9-class bolts (average $F_m / F_{v,Rk}$ equal to 1.20).

Stranghøner et al. [12] proposed to adjust the shear coefficient α_v in Eq. (3a) for property class 8.8 and 10.9 standard bolts, applicable to both threaded and unthreaded sections in the shear plane. Hence, assuming that α_v is taken as 0.6 for both property classes (8.8 and 10.9), the results show good agreement for 10.9 bolts ($F_m / F_{v,Rk}$ equal to 1.00), except for

Table 12
Comparison of experimental and code results for initial stiffness (one bolt in double shear).

Bolt	Class	$K_{v,exp,av}$	$K_{v,EN}$	$K_{v,exp} / K_{v,EN}$	
		Mean (kN/mm)	Mean (kN/mm)	Mean (kN/mm)	CoV (%)
M20	8.8	168.61	368.68	0.46	12.5
	10.9	159.97	459.79	0.35	8.7
M24	8.8	184.81	591.50	0.31	13.3
	10.9	196.28	654.05	0.30	26.9
M27	10.9	252.64	831.44	0.30	12.8
M30	10.9	256.83	1051.26	0.24	18.5
All	8.8	-	-	0.39	22.7
All	10.9	-	-	0.31	20.1
All	All	-	-	0.34	24.7

M30 bolts with property class 10.9, whereby the shear resistance of these bolts is overestimated. Finally, adopting the proposal by Stranghøner et al. [12] of $\alpha_v = 0.65$, the mean $F_m / F_{v,Rk}$ values fall below unity (overall $F_m / F_{v,Rk} = 0.93$ across all tests). This outcome indicates that, for the present experimental results, the proposed modification is not safe.

Fig. 12 and Table 11 compare the experimental and theoretical shear resistance of long bolts, illustrating the influence of varying α_v values. When α_v is increased from the currently proposed 0.5 to 0.6 [27], the R^2 value for 10.9-class bolts increases from 0.666 to 0.970, while the overall R^2 for both property classes improves from 0.798 to 0.981, confirming that the best fit corresponds to $\alpha_v = 0.6$ for both property classes.

Fig. 13. Comparison of theoretical and experimental initial stiffness for long bolts: a) EN; b) Proposed formula.

4.2. Initial stiffness

The elastic deformation of a bolt loaded in shear is a complex problem (e.g. see reference [36]) because it involves the contact between circular surfaces with different radii. It is further complicated for a threaded bolt because the contact surface is discontinuous and prone to local deformation of the threads. Hence, the existing expressions for the initial stiffness of bolts in shear are of an empirical nature, calibrated with experimental test results.

The available expression in EN 1993-1-8 [27], Eq. (6a), depends on the tensile strength of the bolt material, f_{ub} , and the bolt nominal diameter, d , multiplied by a statistically adjusted parameter. Hence, to try to identify possible sources of variability in the experimentally measured initial stiffness, a systematic examination of potential correlations with key mechanical and geometric parameters (e.g. f_{ub} , d , A_s , E) was carried out. Despite this detailed investigation, no statistically significant trends could be established, which could be attributed to the relatively limited size of the experimental dataset (58 valid tests) and the complexity of the problem.

Table 12 presents the experimentally determined shear stiffness values for the bolts, along with the corresponding initial stiffness values K_v calculated using Eq. (6a), scaled by the Young's modulus E to match the experimental values expressed in units of kN/m.

Table 12 shows that Eq. (6a) overestimates the initial stiffness by more than a factor of 2 (overall ratio $K_{v,exp} / K_{v,EN} = 0.34$). This may be partially attributed to the fact that the shear plane is in the threaded part, which is in line with the conclusions by Ahmed and Teh [30] and Lange [31] for standard bolts in shear.

Accordingly, an adjusted expression for the initial stiffness for long bolts in shear is proposed in Eq. (10), based on the obtained experimental results.

$$K_{v,prop.} = \frac{5.4d^2}{d_{M16}} f_{ub} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 13 compares the experimental and the theoretical initial stiffness of long bolts. Eq. (10) exhibits better agreement with the experimental data when compared to the Eurocode Eq. (6a).

The average ratio between the experimental and theoretical initial stiffness values ($K_{v,exp} / K_{v,prop.}$) improved from 0.34 to 1.00 with a similar CoV of 25.3 %, indicating that, despite this improvement, a considerable scatter in the results remains.

Finally, it is worth noting that the scatter of the specifications of the initial stiffness of most joint components is one order of magnitude higher than the specifications of resistance, with typical values ranging from 25 % to 100 % [36]. However, on the positive side, the impact of errors on the initial stiffness is also much lower than errors in the

Table 13

Values of shear factor α_v .

Case	$\alpha_{v,exp}$	
	8.8	10.9
Ref. Case	0.6	0.5
C2	0.6	0.6
C3	0.65	0.65

resistance, thereby compensating for the higher scatter.

5. Reliability assessment

5.1. Methodology

The statistical evaluation is conducted following the procedure outlined in EN 1990, Annex D [15]. A comprehensive description of the methodology is provided in the SAFEBRICTILE project [37] and in Tankova et al. [38], and therefore, only the key findings of the statistical analysis are presented here. For the relevant consequence class CC2 [39], the resulting reliability index (resistance only) is $\beta = 3.04$. The evaluation process follows these steps: (i) defining and statistically characterising the basic variables, (ii) estimating the correction factor b and the coefficient of variation of errors V_σ , and (iii) determining the required partial factor γ_{M2}^* .

5.2. Evaluation of basic variables through a statistical method

The reliability assessment of the shear resistance formula (see Eq. (3a)) for long bolts is based on two basic variables: the tensile strength (f_{ub}) and the tensile stress area (A_s). The long bolts used in this study are consistent with those analysed in [10], as detailed in Section 3.4.2. Therefore, the evaluation of these basic variables in [10] remains applicable to this study and is only briefly summarised below.

In the reference study [10], CoVs were initially derived from independent research. However, the final CoV values were adopted in correspondence with the study by Stranghøner et al. [12], who conducted their own experimental tests and compiled extensive data from existing literature, ensuring a more comprehensive and reliable statistical basis.

5.2.1. Tensile strength

In reference [12], a very large number of test results (394) are collected, comprising 8 distinct test programs and the corresponding material properties are statistically assessed. Stranghøner et al. [12] concluded that the maximum CoV from all these studies is 3.6 % and conservatively adopted a value of 4 %. The results reported in the

Table 14
Reliability assessment of the required partial factor γ_{M2}^* .

Case	Class	α_v (–)	b (–)	V_δ (–)	γ_{M2}^* (–)	b [12] (–)	V_δ [12] (–)	γ_{M2}^* [12] (–)
Ref. Case	All	0.6–0.5	1.138	0.093	1.036	–	–	1.04
	8.8	0.6	1.011	0.026	0.958	1.066	0.050	0.99
	10.9	0.5	1.185	0.044	0.891	1.246	0.034	0.84
C2	All	0.6	0.992	0.038	1.030	–	–	–
	8.8	0.6	1.011	0.026	0.958	–	–	–
	10.9	0.6	0.987	0.044	1.069	–	–	–
C3	All	0.65	0.916	0.038	1.116	–	–	1.15
	8.8	0.65	0.933	0.026	1.038	0.984	0.050	1.07
	10.9	0.65	0.911	0.044	1.158	0.958	0.034	1.09

literature for the tensile strength of bolt material [12] agree very well with the results of the tests reported in reference [10] (CoV from [12] varying between 0.6 % and 3.6 % while the reported results in [10] lead to 3.45 % for 8.8 bolt material and 1.83 % for 10.9 bolt material), showing that there is no reason to differentiate the material properties between standard structural bolts and long bolts, despite the different production process. Hence, in line with the rationale for the preparation of Annex E of EN 1993-1-1 [40], a value of CoV = 4 % was chosen, also for consistency across different studies. In the reference study [10], the tensile strength was evaluated using an augmented dataset combining results from tested and supplementary batches to improve statistical reliability.

5.2.2. Cross-sectional area

The tensile stress area (A_s) is determined based on measurements, using a calliper, of the external and internal diameters and thread pitch, conducted on a sample of long bolts. The calculations of the tensile stress area follow the formulas outlined in ISO 898-1 [11]. The obtained CoV is 0.97 %, which aligns with the 1 % value adopted by Stranghöner et al. [12]. This value is also adopted in [10] and in this study.

5.3. Shear resistance

Reflecting the proposal by Stranghöner et al. [12] to consider a uniform value of $\alpha_v = 0.65$ for both 8.8- and 10.9-classes and for both unthreaded and threaded parts in the shear plane, Table 13 summarises the three cases considered in Section 4.1 for the reliability assessment.

The next step consists of the evaluation of the required partial factor γ_{M2}^* for the three cases defined in Table 13, using Eq. (3a). Table 14 shows that it is not safe to increase α_v from 0.6/0.5 to 0.65, while maintaining the margin for the recommended value of $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$ in EN 1993-1-8 [1]. This margin, as already stated in [10], ensures reliability differentiation as a function of the brittle nature of the failure mode and covers additional unquantified aspects, such as the curvature of the bolts that may also affect the resistance.

6. Conclusions

This paper presents a thorough experimental campaign on long bolts in shear, considering the variability of key parameters such as bolt diameter, bolt class, grip length, and surface finish. A total of 58 valid tests were conducted, leading to the following conclusions:

- The design shear resistance formulas for standard structural bolts in EN 1993-1-8 can be reliably applied to long bolts. The same applies to AISC 360–22 and AS 4100, as they lead to similar results with similar design expressions.
- Considering that the experimental values of F_m are not dependent on the bolt length, it can be concluded that the long bolts in shear behave as bolts and not as pins. However, because of the long unsupported length, long bolts in shear exhibit values of curvature in the range of $L_g / 125$, where L_g is the grip length. This curvature may

become critical should the bolts be subjected to shear and compression.

- The initial stiffness is largely overestimated in EN 1993-1-8 for the shear plane in the threaded part. Based on the test results, a knock-down factor of 0.5 would significantly improve Eq. (6a).
- It is not recommended to increase the shear factor α_v as proposed by Stranghöner et al. [12]. Although the required γ_{M2}^* is lower than the recommended value of $\gamma_{M2}^* = 1.25$, the issue of reliability differentiation for brittle failure modes and redundancy should be discussed in a holistic way across the Structural Eurocodes or, at least, Eurocode 3, and changes should not be implemented in a casuistic way.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Neda Janković: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Filip Ljubinković:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jorge Conde:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jelena Dobrić:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Luís Simões da Silva:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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